

Characterization of the transverse and longitudinal behaviours of PA6.6 monofilaments

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ABSTRACT: In this paper, we study the longitudinal and transverse elastic and viscoelastic behaviours of polyamide 6.6 monofilaments of important diameters (superior to 400 μ m). In most cases, such monofilaments are treated as isotropic elastic cylindrical structures. However, many tests show a strong anisotropy and also a non-elastic behavior. In the first part, we analyze in a traditional way the longitudinal behaviour of such monofilaments, by tensile experiments at different speeds along with relaxation tests which were carried out on a testing machine equipped with special grips. The results show no big difference between the mean experimental tensile curves obtained. In the second part, we investigate the transverse behaviour of these monofilaments. In the beginning, we present a special experimental setup conceived to realize such tests. Secondly, we analyze transverse compression experimental curves at different speeds along with transverse relaxation curves obtained using the previous setup. We show that the transverse behaviour of these monofilaments seems to be strongly elastoplastic and we confirm their high anisotropy.

KEYWORDS: Reinforcements, Testing, Textiles, elastic modulus, anisotropy

INTRODUCTION

Highly oriented polyamide 6.6 monofilaments like those we study are frequently used as reinforcement specially when implanted in polymer matrices. Their anisotropic behaviour is of particular interest in order to estimate for example the mechanical properties of textile structures. Although the longitudinal properties can be easily measured, the transverse behaviour is more difficult to study. For this reason, in this paper we present a special apparatus that we developed in order to access the transverse properties of oriented monofilaments.

Examples of theoretical models treating this problem can be found in literature. The first one is reported by Hadley et al [1] which regarded this kind of monofilaments as transversely isotropic elastic cylinders and obtained a theoretical solution for the width of the contact area between this cylinder and two parallel rigid plates compressing it across its diameter. Then by measurements of the half-contact width, the transverse modulus was found in terms of Poisson's ratio. Later on, Pinnock and Ward [2] extended this result by presenting a theoretical solution for the change in diameter of such a cylinder. By using this model, the transverse modulus was obtained by measures of the diameter change rather than the half-contact zone. Using the theoretical results and the transverse load - displacement results, Phoenix and Skelton [3] developed a technique for calculating the elastic modulus and the

maximum shear stress at yield or fracture. All this theoretical foundation is based on M'Ewen's [4] result for two cylinders in contact along their generatrix.

The object of this paper is to fully study the anisotropic behaviour of PA6.6 monofilaments of important diameter (400 μm). In order to achieve this target, we examine in the first part the longitudinal behaviour by effectuating tensile experiments at different speeds along with relaxation experiments. In the second part, after presenting a special assembly we developed capable to transversely compress a polymer monofilament, we examine compression experimental curves obtained at different speeds along with transverse relaxation curves. The results show a high anisotropy of the PA6.6 monofilament and an important difference between the transverse and longitudinal behaviours.

1 LONGITUDINAL BEHAVIOUR

1.1 EXPERIMENTAL

We submitted PA6.6 monofilaments of 250mm of length and 0.4mm of diameter to tensile experiments. In order to realise such tests, we used a MTS 20M tension - compression machine equipped with special grips. We based our tests on the NF G07-002 French standard under laboratory conditions (temperature: $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity: 65%). Six different speeds were used: 5, 10, 25, 50, 125 and 250 mm/min, which correspond at a strain speeds $\dot{\epsilon}$ between 2 and 100(%)/sec. For each speed a number of 12 to 15 specimens were examined. For the relaxation tests, we used a 5mm/min speed to reach the desired load.

1.2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1, shows a comparison between the mean curves of 12 tensile tests per speed. We can see that the curves are superimposed and that there is no important evolution of quantities like force to rupture as strain speed increases, with the elongation to rupture being the only quantity that seems to change. The mean Young's modulus value is about 2.5GPa. On the contrary, the faces of specimen's rupture differ when increasing strain speed. We show in figure 2 photos of such faces of monofilaments tested at four different speeds: 10, 25, 50 and 125 mm/min (taken at a HITACHI S-2360N Scanning Electron Microscope). It can be concluded from figure 2 that monofilaments "fibrillate" more when decreasing tensile speed, as it is seen by the crack length formed during break. This kind of rupture is characteristic of highly oriented monofilaments like those of aramide or of high-density polyethylene (Haerle [5]). For tensile speeds above 50 mm/min, the monofilament's rupture becomes ductile, as it is seen in figures 2(c) and 2(d). These observations can be explained as follows: for small speeds, molecular chains can be reoriented, displaced and finally detached, which results to the observed "fibrillation" during rupture. As increasing tensile speed, molecular chains simply do not have the time to reorient.

Figure 1: Comparison between mean tensile curves obtained at different speeds

(a) 10mm/min (b) 25mm/min

(c) 50mm/min (d) 125mm/min

Figure 2: S. E. M. Photos of monofilament faces of rupture at four different speeds

Figure 3 shows a comparison between two relaxation curves at different maximum loads. In both cases we stayed in the linear part of the stress - strain curve. We can observe that the polymer examined has a viscoelastic behaviour, with an elastic area been well visible, since the stress decreases slowly. Additionally, there is no apparent residual stress in the monofilament, since no asymptote seems to have been attained. A more detailed explanation of this problem is given by R. H. Blanc and A. Ravasoo [6] who deduced a nonlinear modified constitutive equation for the viscoelastic medium of nylon fibers by using quasi-linear viscoelastic theory and kept the non linear terms up to cubic. Experimental results, presented at the same publication,

are in good agreement with the theoretical model.

Figure 3: Comparison between two relaxation experiments

2 TRANSVERSE BEHAVIOUR

2.1 THEORY

The contact between an isotropic elastic sphere or cylinder and a plate of infinite rigidity, was first studied by Hertz [7], who gave a mathematical expression of the half contact width. Hadley et Al. [1] extended this result for a transverse isotropic cylinder. We consider 1-2 as the plane of transverse isotropy (figure 4) and 3 the monofilament's axis. Thus, we have a problem of plane stress on the plane 1-2. The equation of the half contact width is given by (Hadley [1] and [8]):

$$b = \sqrt{4FR \left(s_{11} - \frac{2}{s_{33}} \right)} \quad (1)$$

where s_{ij} represent the compliance constants, F is the force per unit length and R is the monofilament's radius. In the transverse isotropic case, $s_{11} = 1/E_T$, $s_{33} = 1/E_L$ and $s_{13}/s_{33} = -\nu$, where E_L and E_T are the longitudinal and transverse Young's modulus respectively and ν is the Poisson's ratio.

The approximate equation linking the transverse modulus E_T of a transverse isotropic monofilament and the plate displacement U when $b \ll R$ is given by (Jawad, [9]):

$$U = \frac{4F}{\pi R} \left(\frac{1}{E_T} - \frac{\nu E_T}{E_L} \right) \left[0.19 + \sinh^{-1}(R/b) \right] \quad (2)$$

Where b is the half contact width calculated as explained before. After plotting the evolution of the force per unit length F as a function of the displacement U , Phoenix and Skelton [3] show that the slope $\frac{dF}{dU}$ permits to obtain the transverse modulus by using the equation:

$$\frac{dF}{dU} = \frac{\pi E_T R}{4} \frac{d\hat{F}}{d\hat{U}} \quad (3)$$

where $\hat{F} = \frac{F}{\pi R E_T}$ and $\hat{U} = \frac{U}{4R}$. From theory we can write the expression of dimensionless displacement \hat{U} as a function of dimensionless force:

$$\hat{U} = \hat{F} \left\{ \sinh^{-1} \left(\hat{F}^{-1/2} \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{\hat{F}}} \right) \right\} \quad (4)$$

By differentiating this equation we obtain:

$$\frac{d\hat{F}}{d\hat{U}} = \left\{ \sinh^{\frac{1}{2}}(\hat{F}^{-1/2}) - \frac{1}{2}(1+(\hat{F}+1)^{-1/2}) \right\} \quad (5)$$

Unfortunately, we can't obtain \hat{F} or $\frac{d\hat{F}}{d\hat{U}}$ as explicit functions of \hat{U} . Plots of (4) and (5) when treating \hat{F} as an independent parameter were shown in Phoenix and Skelton [3] and in our previous article [11].

Figure 4: Monofilament's transverse compression

2.2 APPARATUS

The apparatus which is shown in figure 5 was inspired by the Kotani et al. [10] assembly. It is composed of a four column block made of steel and contains three plates, one which is screwed on the MTS 20/M machine named as lower plate (LP), a second one that can move up and down sliding on four steel columns by linear ball bearing joints named as intermediate mobile plate (IMP), and a third one which is screwed on the four columns using a specific couple, in order to achieve a parallel monofilament compression, named as upper plate (UP). The monofilament is transversely compressed between two rigid glass plates with the upper one having a conical form and being held in the UP. The lower glass plate is placed on an aluminium plate which is fixed on a force sensor with screws using a specific couple given by the constructor in order to avoid measurement errors. Therefore, the length of the monofilament loaded is always equal to the diameter of the lower base of the cone (51 mm). The force sensor is placed on the centre of the IMP. This plate is linked to the MTS 20/M tension - compression machine by a four beam frame, the lower one being made from steel and the other three of aluminium in order to avoid having big weights. A steel ball placed on the centre of the lower beam, attains a point contact with the IMP at its centre which was marked with a small cone. This is used to correct any error at the movement of the IMP and to achieve the most parallel possible monofilament compression. The contact zone at the upper glass plate is measured using a Chroma 7310 video microscope. An objective lens is placed on the microscope permitting a 40 times magnification of the image taken. A pair of linear variable displacement transducers (LVDT), which directly "touch" the lower glass plate, is used to measure the compression, the signals from which are averaged to eliminate any several spurious effects resulting from the lower plate movement. The LVDT displacement sensors and the force sensor were calibrated using small plates of known width for the former and pieces of known weights for the latter within their entire measurement interval (0-2000 μ m and 0-2000N respectively). This setup has the big advantage, comparing to the one proposed by Kotani [10], that the tension movement of the machine is used to compress the monofilament. Thus, there is no need to use a spring to counteract the weight of the loading plate, as it was done in the previous work.

Figure 5: Transverse compression setup

2.3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

PA66 monofilaments having a diameter of $400\mu\text{m}$ were transversely compressed using the previous setup until the force of 2000N , which is sufficient enough to squeeze them completely. Three different compression speeds were used: 0.1 , 0.5 and 1mm/min . For each speed a number of 5 specimens were examined. For the relaxation tests, we used a 5mm/min speed to reach the desired load (204N at the first case and 111N at the second one). All these experiments were done under laboratory conditions (temperature: $20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity: 65%). The contact width between the monofilament and the upper glass plate was measured by counting the pixels appearing on the computer screen and it was found that 1 pixel corresponds at $22.22\mu\text{m}$.

2.4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 6 shows the force as a function of the displacement signals obtained from the right and left sensors and their mean values. From the graph we can conclude that the lower glass plate moves parallel to the upper glass plate and consequently the monofilament is uniformly compressed. The evolution of the contact width as it is seen by the microscope is given in Figures 7 (a) and (b).

In Figure 8 we show the mean force-displacement curves obtained for the three different speeds examined. The displacement values, chosen as abscises, are the mean values of the displacement signals obtained by the pair of LVDT sensors, as it was stated before. As we can tell from the results, the three curves seem to be ideal, with small differences resulting probably from mechanical noise due to the down plate movement. However, we can see the monofilament's transverse breaking, which happens at the same level of force (at about 900N) for the three speeds. Continuing transverse compression after this value, results in no response of the monofilament and we can see an almost linear variation of the force as a function of displacement. Even though this phenomenon appears, the contact area continues to change, as it is seen in figure 9, where the evolution of the contact width as a function of the force per unit length is plotted. In the same figure we plot the evolution of the contact width as it is calculated from equation (1) for a transverse isotropic elastic monofilament. We can see that the contact width follows a second degree polynomial evolution until the end of the experiment. This polynomial is plotted by using the least squares method and it is represented by the red curve in the same graph. We can remark that the elastic theoretical values of the contact width and the values measured by the camera "coincide" only at the beginning of the experiment where $b \ll R$, which makes us believe that the elastic area is relatively small. By using the second degree polynomial fit (figure 9), we calculated the missing values of the contact area for every value of the force measured. Making the hypothesis that the mean stress value inside the monofilament can be approximated by:

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{2b \cdot l} \quad (6)$$

where $l=51\text{mm}$ is the diameter of the lower base of the glass cone, b is the half-contact width and F is the force per unit length, we obtain the curve shown in figure 10. We use as abscises the real strain values ($\epsilon^l = \frac{t_r - t_{-r}}{l}$). From this graph we can tell that the monofilament has an elastoplastic behaviour with a Young's modulus being very high and much bigger than the one calculated by the tensile experiments. Thus, the high anisotropy of this kind of monofilaments is confirmed.

The evolution of the force as a function of time during a transverse relaxation experiment is plotted in figure 11, where a comparison between two tests at different initial loadings is given. We can conclude that the relaxation behaviour is slightly viscous, since very rapidly we attain a residual stress, contrary to the longitudinal case. This confirms that the transverse behaviour is viscoelastoplastic and that the elastic area is very short.

 (a) t_1 (sec)

 (b) t_2 (sec)

Figure 6: Typical evolution of the force as a function of displacement (left sensor,
Figures 7(a) and (b): Evolution of the contact width as captured by the

right s values)

microscope ($t_1 < t_2$)

Figure 8: Comparison between force-displacement curves at different speeds

Figure 9: Evolution of the contact width as a function of the force per unit length

Figure 10: Stress-strain curve obtained for a transverse compression experiment

Figure 11: Comparison between two transverse relaxation experiments

CONCLUSION

We have shown in this paper that the polyamide 6.6 monofilaments have a highly anisotropic behaviour. In fact, the results for the transverse compression stress-strain curves make us believe that the material has an elastoplastic response with an elastic area being very small, contrary to the longitudinal experiments. The transverse monofilament's elastic modulus seems to be much higher comparing to the longitudinal one. Even though we stayed in the linear part of the force - displacement curves for both cases during the relaxation tests, we observed a residual stress in the transverse case counter to the longitudinal one where no asymptote seems to have been attained.

This work can be the beginning of a large field of investigation. Further studying of the problem will consist of determining more accurately the transverse behaviour of such specimens, mostly by applying a known tensile force at the monofilament's ends just before the compression experiment.

REFERENCES

1. D.W. HADLEY, I.M. WARD, J. WARD, "The transverse compression of anisotropic fibre monofilaments", *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London A*, 285 (1965), p. 275-286.
2. P.R. PINNOCK, I.M. WARD, J.M. WOLFE, "The compression of anisotropic fibre monofilaments", *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London A*, 291 (1966), p. 267-278.
3. S.L. PHOENIX, J. SKELTON, "Transverse compressive Moduli and Yield Behavior of Some Orthotropic, High-Modulus Filaments", *Textile Research Journal*, 44 (1974) p. 934-940.C.

4. EWEN M'EWEN, 1949, "*The stresses in Elastic Cylinders in Contact along a Generatrix (including the effect of tangential friction)*", *Philosophical Magazine*, p. 454-459.
5. JWS HEARLE, B. LOMAS, WD COOKE, "*Atlas of fibre fracture and damage to textile 2nd edition*", *The Textile Institute - Woohhead publishing* 1998.
6. R.H. BLANC, A.RAVASOO, "*On the nonlinear viscoelastic behaviour of nylon fiber*", *Mechanics of Materials*, 22 (1996) p. 301-310
7. H. HERTZ, *1896 Miscellaneous Papers*, (Mac-Millan, London) p. 146.
8. D.W. HADLEY, P.R. PINNOCK, I.M. WARD, "Anisotropy in Oriented Fibres from Synthetic Polymers", *Journal of materials science*, 4 (1969) p. 152-165.
9. S.A. JAWAD, I.M. WARD, "*The transverse compression of oriented nylon and polyethylene extrudates*", *Journal of materials science*, 13 (1978) p. 1381-1387.
10. T. KOTANI, J. SWEENEY, I.M. WARD, "*The measurement of transverse mechanical properties of polymer fibres*", *Journal of Materials Science*, 29 (1994) p. 5551-5558.
11. G.STAMOULIS, Ch. WAGNER-KOCHER and M.RENNER, "*Characterization of the transverse and longitudinal behaviours of polymer monofilaments*", *JNC13 Conference (France), Mars 2003*, ISBN 2-9505117-5-9.